

ACTIVITY-BASED INSTRUCTIONAL STRATEGY ON SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS' ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT AND RETENTION IN MATHEMATICS IN KOLOKUMA OPUKUMA LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA OF BAYELSA STATE

By

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Abstract.

The study investigated the effect of Activity-Based Instructional Strategy on Secondary School students' academic achievement and retention in Mathematics in Kolokuma Opukuma LGA of Bayelsa State. The study adopted a quasi-experimental design. A sample size of 189 was drawn from the population of 755 students' using purposive sampling techniques. The study was carried out in two groups; the experimental and control. Two intact classes were used for each group. The instrument used was Mathematics Achievement and Retention Test (MART); consisting of past questions from WAEC and NECO related to the mathematical concept on algebra. MART was validated by experts in the field of study. A reliability coefficient index of 0.79 was calculated using Kuder Richardson (KR-20). Two research questions and two hypotheses guided the study. The research questions were answered using the descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation while the hypotheses were tested using (ANCOVA). It was revealed of the study that activity based instructional strategy improved students' academic achievement and retention of learned mathematical concept. Based on the findings it was recommended that teachers should be trained on how to adopt teaching methods that involves hands on activities for better understanding of mathematical concepts.

Keywords: Activity-Based Instructional Strategy, Retention, Academic Achievement, Algebra.

Introduction.

Mathematics is a core subject in Nigerian Educational system at various levels. It is an important subject with a compulsory pass for further studies at each step of educational progress. The knowledge of mathematics is centered towards the development of logical reasoning, problem solving skills and scientific inquire. Mathematics plays a significant role in national development as it is the root to science, technology and engineering knowledge and skills (Awofala, 2017). The significance of mathematics globally is attributed to the unwavering attention accorded to it in our primary, secondary and tertiary schools today. It is observed in our educational system that despite the importance and attention given to mathematics yet, it is of record as one of the most challenging subjects for students in Nigeria and other developing countries, with persistent reports of poor achievement and

low retention among learners (WAEC,2020: Adedayo & Alabi, 2018). This trend raises concern among stakeholders in education and necessitates the adoption of innovative teaching strategies that can improve students' achievement and long-term understanding of the subject.

Traditionally, mathematics teaching in Nigerian secondary schools has been dominated by the lecture or teacher –centered method, where teachers provide explanations while students remain passive recipients (Ogunleye, 2021). This conventional approach has been criticized for failing to actively engage students in the learning process, which often leads to rote memorization rather than meaningful learning and long-term retention (Nwosu & Okeke, 2020). The adverse effect of this on our educational system compelled researchers and educators to emphasize on the need for student-centered instructional strategies that

promote active participation, deeper understanding and sustained interest in mathematics (Abdikerova, 2024).

Activity based instructional strategy has emerged as one of the hopeful approaches for enhancing students' achievement and retention in mathematics. Activity based instructional strategy emphasize on hands on experiences, collaborative learning and problem solving activities that engage students in the construction of their own knowledge (Obara & Okoh, 2021). This is different when compared with the traditional method of teaching mathematics, activity based instructional strategy allows learners to explore mathematical concepts through activities such as games, experiments, group work and real-life problem applications, thereby stimulating critical thinking and promoting deeper understanding (Egbo & Okeke, 2019).

Retention is defined as the ability of students to store information which can be recalled at a later time after exposure to series of instructions or training (Nwosu, & Okeke, 2020). However, it is possible for students to learn concept soon after forgets to recall concept content, less more of application in problem solving. The problem of lack of recollection and application of learned concept in solving mathematical problems is a proof of disconnection in the learning process. This is because the retention ability works together with academic achievement. The cognitive process is of different stages; it involves assimilation, storage, recollection (retrieval) and application, therefore any disruption of the process affects learning. The cognitive process stages depend on the teaching and learning method. The teaching and learning method determines deeper understanding of concepts learned, its retention, application and finally students' academic achievement. Ochigbo and Omaji,

(2025) opined that anything aiding learning should improve retention while anything that causes interference among learned materials decrease efficiency of learning and accelerate forgetting; this may be the reason for poor achievement of students in mathematics. The cognitive processes necessitate the need for teachers to strategize their teaching methodology to achieve effective learning.

Activity based learning aids understanding of what is been learned by building a mental picture of what is learnt stored in the brain and recalled when needed. According to Confucius in Ochigbo and Omaji (2025) the great philosopher "I hear and I forget", "I see and I remember", "I do and I understand" this is very true about mathematics and science learning. Research evidence shows that teaching methods that fully engage students' during the learning process significantly improve their concept understanding and problem-solving skills (Iyekekpolor et al 2024). Retention which refers to the ability of learners to remember and apply learned knowledge after instruction, is a crucial aspect of mathematics learning; because concepts are often interconnected and build progressively across different levels of education (Durojaiye et al, 2021).

The persistent decline in mathematics achievement is a serious concern to our educational system, therefore, calls for an urgent need for strategies that can enhance both achievement and retention. Thus, based on this it becomes imperative the investigation of different teaching approaches and strategies that can fully engage students during learning for positive outcomes. This study therefore, seeks to examine the effect of activity based instructional strategy on students achievement and retention in mathematics, with the aim of providing evidence based recommendations for mathematics teachers and curriculum planners.

Statement of Problem.

Mathematics remains a compulsory subject for all senior secondary school students in Nigeria and it is the foundation to the development of science, technology and innovation (Awofala, 2017). Despite all the efforts of the stakeholders, students' achievement in mathematics at the secondary school level has continued to be a major concern. Several factors have been attributed to this issue of poor achievement in mathematics, among which is the instructional method adopted by teachers.

Most teachers are still teaching mathematics using the talk chalk method which is teacher centered approach, characterized by rote memorization, abstract in nature and poor students' engagement. This teaching method has been widely criticized for failing to promote meaningful learning (Ogunleye, 2021). It is of this reason that students perceived mathematics as a difficult, abstract and irrelevant to real-life experiences which contributes to poor achievement and low retention of knowledge (Adedayo & Alabi 2018). Poor retention of mathematical concepts learned has been identified as one of the reasons why students' achievement in mathematics is poor. Udo and Udofia (2017) revealed in their studies that instructional strategy significantly affects students' achievements and retention in mathematics.

However, evidence of research works of scholars like Egbo and Okeke (2019); Durojaiye et al (2021) confirmed that the continued reliance on traditional methods of teaching mathematics by teachers limit students ability to retain, apply and transfer knowledge to new situation. Thus, the challenging problem regards to persistent poor achievement and low retention of mathematical concepts learned among secondary school students in Nigeria despite

the numerous curriculum reforms, needs an urgent attention. The existing gap between classroom practice and students achievement raises critical questions about how activity based instructional strategies could be employed to address the issue. Retention which is the ability of learners to recall and apply previously gained knowledge in problem solving affects academic achievement and it is dependent on classroom practices. Based on this this study seeks to investigate the effect of activity based instructional strategy on students achievement and retention in mathematics.

Purpose of the study

The purpose of the study is to investigate the effect of activity based instructional strategy on Senior Secondary School students' achievement and retention in mathematics in Kolokuma Opukuma local government area of Bayelsa state. Specifically, the study seeks to;

1. Determine the effect of activity based instructional strategy on senior secondary school students' academic achievement in mathematics.
2. Examine the retention level of senior secondary school students taught mathematics using activity based instructional strategy.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study

1. What is the mean difference on academic achievement level of senior secondary school students taught mathematics using activity based instructional strategy and those taught using the lecture method?
2. What is the retention level of senior secondary school students taught mathematics using activity based instructional strategy?

Hypotheses.

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 significant level

1. There is no significant difference between the academic achievement level of senior secondary school students taught mathematics using activity based instructional strategy and those taught using lecture method
2. There is no significant difference in the retention level of senior secondary school students' after being taught mathematics using activity based instructional strategy.

Research Method

The study was a quasi-experimental design; classes were used in their intact nature. The researcher adopted pretest-posttest non randomization of subjects into the treatment and control group. The population of the study comprises of (755) senior secondary school one (SS1) students in Kolokuma Opukuma local government area of Bayelsa state for 2024/2025 academic session. (source: Bayelsa State Ministry of Education).

The sample size of the study was (189) SS1 students in their intact classes in the four secondary school used. Purposive sampling was used in selecting schools with a functional science or mathematics laboratory. Two schools with a functional science/mathematics laboratory were used for the experimental group while two schools were used for the control group. A total number of (94) students' was used for experimental group while (95) students were used for the control group. The instrument used was Mathematics Achievement and Retention Test (MART).

The instrument Mathematics Achievement and Retention Test (MART) contained 10 multiple questions on algebra from West Africa Examination Council (WAEC) and National Examination Council (NECO) past questions. The instrument was validated by lecturers in the department of Science Education, Faculty of Education; Federal

University Otuoke. The test for reliability of the instrument; 20 students' randomly were selected from senior secondary schools one (SS1) that did not participate in the study, but are of the same characteristics with the population. A reliability index of 0.79 was calculated using Kuder-Richardson (KR-20).

At first a Pre-MART was administered to students before the commencement of the two weeks lesson to both groups. The scores were collected. A well-designed lesson plan on algebra was used to teach the control group for two weeks using the lecture method and with the assistance of two mathematics teachers. The experimental group was taught using lesson package designed based activity-based instructional strategy. The lesson involves hands on activity as students learned through exploration of the environment applying real life situation and manipulating available improvised instructional materials such as algebra tiles, balance scales, were used to explore equations, variables and functions. At the end of the two weeks lesson a Post- MART was given to both groups and scores obtained were recorded for analyses.

After three weeks, a post post-test was given to the experimental group; a similar and related test just a disguise of MART. The post post-test was used to test students' retention ability level. At the end of the test scores generated were recorded for analyses.

The research questions were answered using the descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation while the hypotheses were tested using the Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) at 0.05 significant level.

Research Question 1: What is the mean difference on academic achievement of senior secondary school students taught mathematics using activity based instructional strategy and those taught using the lecture method?

TABLE 1: ACHIEVEMENT MEAN SCORES AND STANDARD DEVIATION OF STUDENTS IN EXPERIMENTAL AND CONTROL GROUPS.

Groups	N	Pre-MART		Post-MART	
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Experimental	94	6.04	2.25	16.96	2.12
Control	95	5.88	2.10	10.75	2.26
Mean Difference		0.16		6.21	
Total	189				

Table 1, showed that in the Pre-MART, the experimental group had achievement mean score of 6.04 with a standard deviation of 2.25, while the control group had achievement mean score of 5.88 with a standard deviation of 2.10. Their mean difference was 0.16. The Table also indicated that in the Post-MART, the experimental group had achievement mean score of 16.96 with a standard deviation

of 2.12, while the control group had achievement mean score of 10.75 with a standard deviation of 2.26. Based on the achievement mean scores (Post-MART) of students of the two groups, a mean difference of 6.21 was recorded.

Research Question Two: What is the retention level of senior secondary school students taught mathematics using activity based instructional strategy?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of the Experimental Group Indicating Level of Retentiveness

Group	N	Post-MART		Post Post-MART		Mean Gain
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
Expt	94	16.96	2.12	16.74	1.94	0.22
Total	94	-	-	-	-	-

The findings of Table 2, showed that the Post-MART scores of the experimental group has an achievement mean score of 16.96 and a standard deviation of 2.12, while the Post Post-MART had achievement mean score of 16.74 with a standard deviation of 1.96. A mean gain of 0.22 was recorded.

Hypothesis one: There is no significant difference between the academic achievement level of senior secondary school students taught mathematics using activity based instructional strategy and those taught using lecture method

Table 3: ANCOVA Result of Students Achievement Scores.

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects

Dependent Variable: posttest

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Squared	Eta
Corrected Model	1862.227 ^a	2	931.113	201.453	.000	.684	
Intercept	3484.162	1	3484.162	753.824	.000	.802	
Pretest	40.078	1	40.078	8.671	.004	.045	
Group	1800.027	1	1800.027	389.449	.000	.677	
Error	859.689	186	4.622				
Total	38903.000	189					
Corrected Total	2721.915	188					

a. R Squared = .684 (Adjusted R Squared = .681)

Table 3 shows that, the analysis result of students taught mathematics in the experimental and control groups has a P value of 0.00 which is less than (<) 0.05 level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis of no significant difference is rejected, thus alternative accepted. This implied that there is significant differences in the achievement mean score of students taught mathematics

using activity-based instructional strategy and those taught using lecture method, thereby indicating favor of the experimental group.

Hypothesis two: There is no significant difference in the retention level of senior secondary school students’ after being taught mathematics using activity based instructional strategy.

Table 4: ANCOVA Result of Students Retention Level.

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects

Dependent Variable: VAR00002

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Squared	Eta
Corrected Model	1.391 ^a	2	.695	.151	.860	.002	
Intercept	6325.288	1	6325.288	1377.736	.000	.882	
VAR00001	.194	1	.194	.042	.837	.000	
VAR00003	1.220	1	1.220	.266	.607	.001	
Error	849.349	185	4.591				
Total	55421.000	188					
Corrected Total	850.739	187					

a. R Squared = .002 (Adjusted R Squared = -.009)

Table 4 shows that, ANCOVA result of the experimental group on retention has a P value of 0.602 which is greater than (>) 0.05 significance level. The null hypothesis of no significant difference is accepted. This implies that there is no significant difference in the retention level of students’ taught using activity-based instructional strategy.

Discussion of Findings.

The Findings of this study proved that students of the experimental group taught using activity based instructional strategy achieved better than their counterpart and maintained high retention level of concept learned. This result agrees with the famous Chinese proverb which says “I hear I forget, I see I remember, I do I understand”. The study authenticate the findings of Nwamaradi and Arinze (2024) that students taught with

activity based method of instruction achieved higher and retained the concept of circle geometry more than those taught with lecture method.

The study is in agreement with study of Azuka (2013) and Agah et al (2024) which attested that activity based method increases students understanding of mathematical concepts learned which impact positively in their academic achievement. It is also in line with the study of Omolafe et al (2024) which revealed that students taught mathematical concept using activity based method performed better than their counterpart in the control group. The study supports the study of Ochigbo and Omaji (2025) though in basic science in their investigation revealed that students taught using activity-based teaching approach improved in their achievement and retention level. It was also of the same opinion with Udo and Udofia (2017) in their study reported that activity based strategies enhanced not only achievement but also the retention of mathematical concepts over time.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that activity-based instructional strategy enhances students' academic achievement in mathematics and also improves their retention level on mathematical concepts learned.

Recommendation

Based on the findings of the study the following recommendations were made;

1. Teachers should incorporate activity based instructional teaching methods into mathematics lessons to enhance students' engagement and understanding.
2. School administrators should support professional development of teachers on how to implement activity based instructional teaching and provide the

necessary resources and materials needed.

3. Curriculum developers and planners should include guidelines that incorporate teaching methods in mathematics education.
4. Government should provide schools with standard mathematics laboratory for effective teaching and learning of mathematics and science subject.

References

- Abdikerova, Z. (2024). Innovative approaches to teaching fundamental concepts in school mathematics: A comparative study. *Eurasian Science Review* 2(4) ISSN 3006-1164.
- Adedayo, A. & Alabi, T. O. (2018). Teachers' pedagogical approaches and students' performance in mathematics in Nigeria secondary schools. *International Journal of Education and Practice*, 6(4), 199-210.
- Agah, M. P., Ibrahim, A. A. & Shuaibu, H. (2024). Effect of activity-based instructional strategy on senior secondary school students academic achievement in mathematics in Numan Education zone, Adamawa state, Nigeria. *Bushwealth Academic Journal*. Retrieved from <https://bwjournal.org/index.php/bsjournal/article/view/2292>.
- Awofala, A. O. (2017). Curriculum value orientation and reform in mathematics education in Nigeria. *Abacus: The Journal of the Mathematics Association of Nigeria*, 42(1), 173-187.
- Azuka, B. F. (2013). Activity-based learning strategies in the mathematics classroom. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 4(13), 173-192.
- Durojaiye, D. S., Jakayinfa, O. J. & Olada, F. S. (2021). Effect of activity-based

- instructional strategy on senior secondary school students retention in circle geometry in Abuja, Nigeria. *European Journal of Education Studies*, 8(10), 79-93.
- Egbo, J. O., & Okeke, C. I. (2019). Enhancing students' achievement in mathematics using activity-based learning strategy. *Nigerian Journal of Mathematics and Science Education*, 15(2), 44-55.
- Iyekekpolor, S. A., Shiaki, O.B. & Uverueh, I. (2024). Effect of conceptual instructional strategy on students achievement and retention in geometry in Delta state, Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovative Social and Science Education Research*, 12(2), 115-126.
- National Examinations Council (NECO). (2019). Chief Examiners' Report on June/July Senior School Certificate Examination. Mina: NECO.
- Nwamaradi, T. A. & Arinze, C. (2024) Effect of Activity-Based Method of Instruction on Secondary School Students' Academic Achievement on Circle Geometry. *Unizik Journal of Educational Research and Policy Studies* 17(3).
- Nwosu, J. & Okeke, C. (2020). Teacher-centered versus student-centered approaches in mathematics classroom: Implications for learners' retention. *African Journal of Educational Research*, 24(1), 67-79.
- Obara, J. A., & Okoh, E. (2021). Activity-based instructional strategy and students' achievement in mathematics: Implications for effective teaching. *Journal of Education and Instructional Studies in the World*, 11(1), 32-40.
- Ochigbo, A. C., & Omaji, R. (2025). Effect of activity-based teaching strategy on academic achievement and retention in basic concepts in upper basic level in Makurdi, Benue State, Nigeris. *Journal of Contemporary Education*, 8(1).
- Ogunleye, A. O. (2021). The effectiveness of innovative teaching strategies in mathematics classrooms. *Journal of Education and practice*, 12(18), 56-63.
- Omolafe, E., Okikiayo, A. & Eyiemi (2024). Effect of Activity Based Teaching Strategy on Students' Academic Performance in Mathematics Concept. *International Journal of Instructional Technology and Educational Studies (IJITES)* 5(3) ISSN (online) 2682-3926
- Owolabi, J., & Akinoso, O. (2015). The effects of instructional strategies on students' retention in mathematics in Lagos State. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 6(17), 79-86.
- Udo, E. J., & Udofia, I. E. (2017). Effect of activity-based teaching strategy on students' academic achievement and retention in geometry. *International Journal of Innovative Education Research*, 5(4), 74-80.
- WAEC. (2020). Chief examiners' report: West African Senior School Certificate Examination. Lagos: WAEC.